

Electronic Supplementary Material for

Aligning paleobiological research with conservation priorities using elasmobranchs as a model

Erin M. Dillon and Catalina Pimiento *

Erin M. Dillon. Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute, Balboa, Republic of Panama. E-mail: dillone@si.edu

Catalina Pimiento. Department of Paleontology, University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland; Department of Biosciences, Swansea University, Swansea, United Kingdom; Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute, Balboa, Republic of Panama. E-mail: catalina.pimientofernandez@pim.uzh.ch

* Corresponding author

This PDF file contains:

Table 1 Supplementary Information

Supplementary References

Table 1 Supplementary Information

We provide brief justifications below to support how we scored the potential contributions of near- and deep-time geohistorical records to each priority question identified by Jorgensen et al. (2022). The scores are presented in Table 1. Contributions were defined as being major (e.g., relevant data are available and directly applicable), minor (e.g., some relevant data exist but their application is less tangible or hindered by biases and/or mismatches in resolution), minimal (e.g., few relevant data exist but they could hypothetically contribute), or none (e.g., no relevant data are available or the question is out of scope). When the potential contribution is minor or major, we direct readers to the corresponding article header.

Status and threats

How do we overcome data deficiency in elasmobranch population assessments?

Near-time: Minor, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. Near-time geohistorical records could serendipitously capture information about the past abundance or geographic range of extant Data Deficient species, extinctions or extirpations in the recent past not captured by monitoring data, or traits associated with extinction that could help predict the conservation status of Data Deficient species (Kowalewski et al. 2023; see the deep-time justification for more details). Such data could help contextualize elasmobranch population assessments, although would not be available for all species, regions, or habitats and are constrained by their taxonomic and temporal resolution (especially since the IUCN Red List uses 1500 CE as a cut-off year). Historical records could also be used to fill data gaps (Raicevich and Fortibuoni 2013; Pérez-Jiménez 2014; Leonetti et al. 2020) to improve estimates of long-term population change to unshift the baselines used in IUCN assessments. See Topic 4.

Deep-time: Minor, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. Intrinsic traits correlated with extinction risk have the potential to predict the status of species that are Data Deficient or Not Evaluated on the IUCN Red List. This has been done for other taxa such as amphibians (Tietje and Rödel 2018) and corals (Raja et al. 2021). Relevant ecological and life-history traits can be measured in the elasmobranch fossil record (e.g., Cooper et al. 2023), and elasmobranchs have endured multiple extinction events over their evolutionary history, so they could be a useful clade for such analyses (Kriwet et al. 2008). In some scenarios, relevant information might be available directly from fossils because 10% of extant elasmobranch species have a fossil record, including some Data Deficient species (Paillard et al. 2021). Uncertainty when measuring traits, challenges with trait conservatism, and the inherent incompleteness in the fossil record limit the direct application of these data in population assessments, as does the focus of the IUCN Red List criteria on population-level trends in abundance and geographic range. See Topic 4.

How can we improve life history estimations of elasmobranchs for fisheries management and conservation?

Near-time: Minor, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. Some life-history traits can be inferred from fossil teeth (e.g., body size; Cooper et al. 2023) and vertebral rings (e.g., growth and age; Shimada 2008), although not all relevant traits can be measured (e.g., fecundity or length-at-maturity) or measured at a taxonomic resolution that is appropriate to inform management. Vertebrae are less common than teeth in the fossil record, although can be recovered from archaeological sites (Burg Mayer and de Freitas 2023). See Topics 2 and 4.

Deep-time: Minor, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. The deep-time record faces the same challenges as the near-time record, although has lower representation by extant species that would be directly applicable to management. Nonetheless, when faced with data deficiency, phylogenetically conserved aspects of life history could be used in models to estimate extinction risk or other phylogenetically conserved traits. See Topics 2 and 4.

What are the most effective and promising approaches for elasmobranch bycatch mitigation?

Near-time: Minimal, constrained by data availability, scale/resolution, and how the question is framed (in terms of human behavioral changes). Near-time geohistorical records could help locate hotspots of elasmobranch abundance or biodiversity (e.g., Carrillo-Briceño et al. 2018) that could be flagged for protection and avoided by fisheries to help mitigate bycatch. Additionally, historical records occasionally contain elasmobranch bycatch data (e.g., Bom et al. 2020), which could be used to quantify the impact of bycatch although not necessarily change fishing methods and/or gear.

Deep-time: No envisioned application because bycatch is a recent threat and the question is framed in terms of human behavioral changes.

How can we more accurately measure and monitor total global catch of elasmobranchs?

Near-time: Minimal, constrained by data availability, scale/resolution, and how the question is framed. Near-time geohistorical records for elasmobranchs often do not have the temporal or taxonomic resolution to measure recent industrial fishing impacts (or catch specifically, as the question is framed), and available records are limited to specific habitats like coral reefs. However, they can provide long-term historical context about fishing pressure or pre-exploitation abundances (e.g., Dillon et al. 2021). On the other hand, logbooks and other archival data (when available) can be used to reconstruct historical catches (e.g., Ferretti et al. 2008; Saldaña-Ruiz et al. 2017), which might be more relevant for addressing this question as framed, although they suffer from similar reporting issues as modern landings data.

Deep-time: No envisioned application because fishing is a recent threat and the question is framed from the perspective of what is being caught.

Beyond fishing, what are the emerging threats to elasmobranchs?

Near-time: Major. See Topic 3.

Deep-time: Major. See Topic 3.

How can we reconstruct elasmobranch baselines to inform population decline estimations and recovery targets?

Near-time: Major. See Topic 1.

Deep-time: Minimal, constrained by scale. Deep-time geohistorical records can contextualize the evolution of modern ecosystem structure (Sibert and Norris 2015; Sibert et al. 2016) but typically do not provide ecological baselines that are relevant for estimating declines in extant populations. Environmental conditions and community structure were different millions of years ago, so they less useful for informing current conservation recovery targets. See Topic 1.

Population and ecology

What are the knowledge gaps in global abundance and diversity of elasmobranchs?

Near-time: Major. See Topics 1 and 4.

Deep-time: Major. See Topics 1 and 4.

How can tagging technologies be applied more effectively to inform elasmobranch research and conservation?

Near-time: Minimal, and applicable only if the question is reframed in terms of elasmobranch movement or spatial ecology rather than tagging technologies. Tags are a modern invention, but methods like stable isotope analysis (i.e., $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, and $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) could be used to trace elasmobranch movement across isotopically distinct water bodies and fingerprint their use of energetic resources from different habitats (Fischer et al. 2013). For example, Taylor et al. (2019) tracked whale migrations in the Pleistocene using oxygen isotopes, demonstrating the utility of this approach more broadly. See Topic 2.

Deep-time: See the near-time justification above.

How can we more clearly define the ecological role of elasmobranchs?

Near-time: Major. See Topic 2.

Deep-time: Major. See Topic 2.

How can we improve knowledge of elasmobranch population structures?

Near-time: Minimal, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. The types of information needed to address this question, such as genetic variation and demographic data, are not readily preserved in the fossil record. However, methods to analyze ancient DNA from elasmobranch fossils and historical specimens are advancing (e.g., Gubili et al. 2015; Fioravanti et al. 2020; Shepherd and Campbell 2021). Note that the recovery of ancient DNA becomes more difficult in older specimens and depends on the depositional environment.

Deep-time: See the near-time justification above.

Conservation and management

What is the role of citizen science in elasmobranch conservation research?

Near-time: Minor, given the potential for advocational paleontologists and other members of the public to find elasmobranch fossils (see the deep-time justification for more details, noting that deep-time fossils are more commonly encountered). Additionally, one could consider historical archives to be a form of retrospective “citizen science.”

Deep-time: Major, given the potential for advocational paleontologists and other members of the public to find elasmobranch fossils such as shark teeth, thereby contributing to and learning from paleontological collections which could, in turn, inform conservation (e.g., Visaggi and Godfrey 2010). Additionally, fossils themselves capture the imagination and could be used to inspire conservation action. Deep-time deposits containing elasmobranch fossils tend to be more accessible to the public.

How can marine protected areas (MPAs) contribute to elasmobranch conservation?

Near-time: Minor, constrained by data availability, scale/resolution, and how the question is framed (in terms of implementation and the biological outcomes of MPAs). Near-time geohistorical (including archaeological) and historical records could help identify areas in need of protection by setting historical baselines and documenting population changes (e.g., Shephard et al. 2019; Fossile et al. 2020; Dillon et al. 2021). See Topic 4.

Deep-time: Minor, constrained by data availability, scale/resolution, and how the question is framed (in terms of implementation and the biological outcomes of MPAs). Deep-time records could be used to map hotspots of threatened biodiversity (e.g., Finnegan et al. 2015) and anticipate shifts in habitat use under future climate change scenarios (e.g., Villafaña et al. 2020), which could inform MPA placement. See Topic 4.

Under what conditions (ecological, environmental, social, and political) can elasmobranch fisheries be sustainable?

Near-time: Minor, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. Although the social and political aspects of this question are largely out of scope (although see Rick et al. 2002), historical baselines derived from near-time geohistorical and historical records could help explore the ecological or environmental contexts under which fishing might be more sustainable and/or identify areas that might be more resilient to fishing pressure. Importantly, archaeological data can document past fishing practices and assess their long-term sustainability (Erlandson and Rick 2010; Lambrides and Weisler 2016; Barrett 2019; Toso et al. 2021). See Topic 1.

Deep-time: No envisioned application as the temporal scale is recent and the social and political aspects of the question are out of scope.

What is the socio-economic role of elasmobranch fisheries?

Near-time: Minor, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. Information about the numbers and body sizes of harvested elasmobranchs derived from near-time geohistorical (especially from archaeological sites; Rick et al. 2002; Fossile et al. 2019; Toso et al. 2021; Prieto 2023) and historical records (e.g., Ferretti et al. 2008; Engelhard et al. 2016) could provide a long-term record of historical fishing and marine resource use to help reconstruct the historical socio-economic importance of elasmobranchs as a source of protein. See Topic 1.

Deep-time: No envisioned application as the temporal scale is recent and because the social and economic aspects of the question are out of scope.

How can we quantify ecosystem services provided by elasmobranchs?

Near-time: Minor, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. Elasmobranch remains and cultural artifacts at archaeological sites (e.g., de Borhegyi 1961; López de la Lama et al. 2020; Fossile et al. 2023) could be useful for addressing this question from the perspective of food, culture, and spirituality. Additionally, stable isotope analyses can be used to investigate the wider ecological roles of elasmobranchs, such as promoting ecosystem connectivity, which influence their ecosystem services (e.g., Burg Mayer and de Freitas 2023). See Topic 2.

Deep-time: No envisioned application as the temporal scale is recent and because ecosystem services pertain to humans.

What is the role of vessel tracking in assessing and enforcing fisheries interactions with elasmobranchs?

Near-time: No envisioned application as the question deals with a recent technology.

Deep-time: See the near-time justification above.

What are the relative impacts of small-scale, industrial, and recreational fisheries on elasmobranch populations?

Near-time: Minor, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. Near-time geohistorical records often do not have the temporal or taxonomic resolution to disentangle the direct impacts of different types of fisheries (especially recreational vs. industrial), and available records are limited to specific habitats like coral reefs. Nevertheless, they could provide long-term historical context about fishing pressure or pre-exploitation abundances (e.g., Dillon et al. 2021). On the other hand, logbooks and other archival data (when available) have been used to reconstruct historical catches over more recent timescales, making them more useful for addressing this question. For example, Ferretti et al. (2008) combined commercial and recreational fisheries landings data, and McClenachan (2009) analyzed photos of recreationally caught trophy fish. Note that this question is framed in terms of the biological impacts rather than from the perspective of catch, such that geohistorical data are more relevant. See Topic 3.

Deep-time: No envisioned application because fishing is a recent threat.

How can we reconcile public safety and healthy elasmobranch populations?

Near-time: Minimal, constrained by data availability, scale/resolution, and how the question is framed (in terms of human behavior). Nevertheless, near-time geohistorical records could contribute relevant information about historical baselines (i.e., what a healthy elasmobranch population might look like; Dillon et al. 2021) and are useful from an educational standpoint (i.e., to manage risk perception).

Deep-time: No envisioned application as the temporal scale is very recent and because the aspects of the question pertaining to human-wildlife conflict are out of scope.

What are the species composition and population impacts of the shark fin trade?

Near-time: Minimal, constrained by data availability and scale/resolution. This question is mostly out of scope because near-time geohistorical records often do not have the temporal or taxonomic resolution to measure the direct impacts of the fin trade. Nevertheless, they could provide long-term historical context about fishing pressure or pre-exploitation abundances. On the other hand, historical documents relating to the fin trade (when available) might be more useful for addressing this question (e.g., Clarke 2008).

Deep-time: No envisioned application because the fin trade is a recent threat.

What are the impacts of regulations across elasmobranch species and jurisdictional scales?

Near-time: No envisioned application as the temporal scale is very recent and the question is framed in terms of human behavioral changes and their biological outcomes.

Deep-time: See the near-time justification above.

Supplementary References

- Barrett, J. H. 2019: An environmental (pre)history of European fishing: past and future archaeological contributions to sustainable fisheries. *Journal of Fish Biology* 94:1033–1044.
- Bom, R. A., M. van de Water, K. C. J. Camphuysen, H. W. van der Veer, and A. van Leeuwen. 2020: The historical ecology and demise of the iconic Angelshark *Squatina squatina* in the southern North Sea. *Marine Biology* 167:91.
- de Borhegyi, S. F. 1961: Shark teeth, stingray spines, and shark fishing in Ancient Mexico and Central America. *Southwestern Journal of Anthropology* 17:273–296.
- Burg Mayer, G., and R. H. A. de Freitas. 2023: Archaeological sharks: changes in the trophic ecology between late Holocene and modern shark communities in South Brazil. *Marine Biology* 170:102.
- Carrillo-Briceño, J. D., O. A. Aguilera, and F. Rodriguez. 2014: Fossil Chondrichthyes from the central eastern Pacific Ocean and their paleoceanographic significance. *Journal of South American Earth Sciences* 51:76–90.
- Clarke, S. 2008: Use of shark fin trade data to estimate historic total shark removals in the Atlantic Ocean. *Aquatic Living Resources* 21:373–381.
- Cooper, J. A., J. N. Griffin, R. Kindlimann, and C. Pimiento. 2023: Are shark teeth proxies for functional traits? A framework to infer ecology from the fossil record. *Journal of Fish Biology* 103:798–814.
- Dillon, E. M., D. J. McCauley, J. M. Morales-Saldaña, N. D. Leonard, J. Zhao, and A. O’Dea. 2021: Fossil dermal denticles reveal the preexploitation baseline of a Caribbean coral reef shark community. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 118:e2017735118.
- Engelhard, G. H., R. H. Thurstan, B. R. MacKenzie, H. K. Alleway, R. C. A. Bannister, M. Cardinale, M. W. Clarke, J. C. Currie, T. Fortibuoni, P. Holm, S. J. Holt, C. Mazzoldi, J. K. Pinnegar, S. Raicevich, F. A. M. Volckaert, E. S. Klein, and A.-K. Lescrauwaet. 2016: ICES meets marine historical ecology: placing the history of fish and fisheries in current policy context. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 73:1386–1403.
- Erlandson, J. M., and T. C. Rick. 2010: Archaeology meets marine ecology: the antiquity of maritime cultures and human impacts on marine fisheries and ecosystems. *Annual Review of Marine Science* 2:231–251.
- Ferretti, F., R. A. Myers, F. Serena, and H. K. Lotze. 2008: Loss of large predatory sharks from the Mediterranean Sea. *Conservation Biology* 22:952–964.
- Finnegan, S., S. C. Anderson, P. G. Harnik, C. Simpson, D. P. Tittensor, J. E. Byrnes, Z. V. Finkel, D. R. Lindberg, L. H. Liow, R. Lockwood, H. K. Lotze, C. R. McClain, J. L. McGuire, A. O’Dea, and J. M. Pandolfi. 2015: Paleontological baselines for evaluating extinction risk in the modern oceans. *Science* 348:567–570.
- Fioravanti, T., F. Bargnesi, A. Splendiani, M. Giovannotti, F. Renzi, and V. Caputo Barucchi. 2020: Historical DNA as a tool to genetically characterize the Mediterranean sand tiger

- shark (*Carcharias taurus*, Lamniformes: Odontaspidae): a species probably disappeared from this basin. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 30:892–902.
- Fischer, J., J. W. Schneider, S. Voigt, M. M. Joachimski, M. Tichomirowa, T. Tütken, J. Götze, and U. Berner. 2013: Oxygen and strontium isotopes from fossil shark teeth: environmental and ecological implications for Late Palaeozoic European basins. *Chemical Geology* 342:44–62.
- Fossile, T., J. Ferreira, D. da Rocha Bandeira, L. Figuti, S. Dias-da-Silva, N. Hausmann, H. K. Robson, D. Orton, and A. C. Colonese. 2019: Pre-Columbian fisheries catch reconstruction for a subtropical estuary in South America. *Fish and Fisheries* 20:1124–1137.
- Fossile, T., J. Ferreira, D. da R. Bandeira, S. Dias-da-Silva, and A. C. Colonese. 2020: Integrating zooarchaeology in the conservation of coastal-marine ecosystems in Brazil. *Quaternary International* 545:38–44.
- Fossile, T., D. F. Herbst, K. McGrath, A. Toso, P. C. F. Giannini, R. G. Milheira, S.-P. Gilson, J. Ferreira, D. da R. Bandeira, M. Haimovici, B. Ceretta, M. G. Bender, and A. C. Colonese. 2023: Bridging archaeology and marine conservation in the Neotropics. *PLOS ONE* 18:e0285951.
- Gubili, C., C. E. C. Robinson, G. Cliff, S. P. Wintner, E. de Sabata, S. D. Innocentiis, S. Canese, D. W. Sims, A. P. Martin, L. R. Noble, and C. S. Jones. 2015: DNA from historical and trophy samples provides insights into white shark population origins and genetic diversity. *Endangered Species Research* 27:233–241.
- Jorgensen, S., F. Micheli, T. White, K. Van Houtan, J. Alfaro-Shigueto, S. Andrzejaczek, N. Arnoldi, J. Baum, B. Block, G. Britten, C. Butner, S. Caballero, D. Cardeñosa, T. Chapple, S. Clarke, E. Cortés, N. Dulvy, S. Fowler, A. Gallagher, E. Gilman, B. Godley, R. Graham, N. Hammerschlag, A. Harry, M. Heithaus, M. Hutchinson, C. Huveneers, C. Lowe, L. Lucifora, T. MacKeracher, J. Mangel, A. Barbosa Martins, D. McCauley, L. McClenachan, C. Mull, L. Natanson, D. Pauly, D. Pazmiño, J. Pistevo, N. Queiroz, G. Roff, B. Shea, C. Simpfendorfer, D. Sims, C. Ward-Paige, B. Worm, and F. Ferretti. 2022: Emergent research and priorities for shark and ray conservation. *Endangered Species Research* 47:171–203.
- Kowalewski, M., R. Nawrot, D. Scarponi, A. Tomašových, and M. Zuschin. 2023: Marine conservation palaeobiology: what does the late Quaternary fossil record tell us about modern-day extinctions and biodiversity threats? *Cambridge Prisms: Extinction*:1–47.
- Kriwet, J., W. Kiessling, and S. Klug. 2008: Diversification trajectories and evolutionary life-history traits in early sharks and batoids. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 276:945–951.
- Lambrides, A. B. J., and M. I. Weisler. 2016: Pacific Islands ichthyoarchaeology: implications for the development of prehistoric fishing studies and global sustainability. *Journal of Archaeological Research* 24:275–324.

- Leonetti, F. L., E. Sperone, A. Travaglini, A. R. Mojetta, M. Signore, P. N. Psomadakis, T. M. Dinkel, and M. Bottaro. 2020: Filling the gap and improving conservation: how IUCN Red Lists and historical scientific data can shed more light on threatened sharks in the Italian seas. *Diversity* 12:389.
- López de la Lama, R., S. Puente, J. C. Sueiro, and K. M. A. Chan. 2021: Reconnecting with the past and anticipating the future: a review of fisheries-derived cultural ecosystem services in pre-Hispanic Peru. *People and Nature* 3:129–147.
- McClenachan, L. 2009: Documenting loss of large trophy fish from the Florida Keys with historical photographs. *Conservation Biology* 23:636–643.
- Paillard, A., K. Shimada, and C. Pimiento. 2021: The fossil record of extant elasmobranchs. *Journal of Fish Biology* 98:445–455.
- Pérez-Jiménez, J. C. 2014: Historical records reveal potential extirpation of four hammerhead sharks (*Sphyrna* spp.) in Mexican Pacific waters. *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries* 24:671–683.
- Prieto, G. 2023: Shark fisheries during the second millennium BC in Gramalote, north coast of Peru. *The Journal of Island and Coastal Archaeology* 18:165–195.
- Raicevich, S., and T. Fortibuoni. 2013: Assessing neoextirpations in the Adriatic Sea: an historical ecology approach. *CIESM Workshop Monographs* 97–111.
- Raja, N. B., A. Lauchstedt, J. M. Pandolfi, S. W. Kim, A. F. Budd, and W. Kiessling. 2021: Morphological traits of reef corals predict extinction risk but not conservation status. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 30:1597–1608.
- Rick, T. C., J. M. Erlandson, M. A. Glassow, and M. L. Moss. 2002: Evaluating the economic significance of sharks, skates, and rays (Elasmobranchs) in prehistoric economies. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 29:111–122.
- Saldaña-Ruiz, L. E., O. Sosa-Nishizaki, and D. Cartamil. 2017: Historical reconstruction of Gulf of California shark fishery landings and species composition, 1939–2014, in a data-poor fishery context. *Fisheries Research* 195:116–129.
- Shephard, S., C. Wögerbauer, P. Green, J. Ellis, and W. Roche. 2019: Angling records track the near extirpation of angel shark *Squatina squatina* from two Irish hotspots. *Endangered Species Research* 38:153–158.
- Shepherd, L. D., and M. Campbell. 2021: Ancient DNA analysis of an archaeological assemblage of Chondrichthyes vertebrae from South Auckland, New Zealand. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 36:102830.
- Shimada, K. 2008: Ontogenetic parameters and life history strategies of the late Cretaceous lamniform shark, *Cretoxyrhina mantelli*, based on vertebral growth increments. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 28:21–33.
- Sibert, E., R. Norris, J. Cuevas, and L. Graves. 2016: Eighty-five million years of Pacific Ocean gyre ecosystem structure: long-term stability marked by punctuated change. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 283:20160189.

- Sibert, E. C., and R. D. Norris. 2015: New age of fishes initiated by the Cretaceous–Paleogene mass extinction. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 112:8537–8542.
- Taylor, L. D., A. O’Dea, T. J. Bralower, and S. Finnegan. 2019: Isotopes from fossil coronulid barnacle shells record evidence of migration in multiple Pleistocene whale populations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 116:7377–7381.
- Tietje, M., and M.-O. Rödel. 2018: Evaluating the predicted extinction risk of living amphibian species with the fossil record. *Ecology Letters* 21:1135–1142.
- Toso, A., E. Hallingstad, K. McGrath, T. Fossile, C. Conlan, J. Ferreira, D. da Rocha Bandeira, P. C. F. Giannini, S.-P. Gilson, L. de Melo Reis Bueno, M. Q. R. Bastos, F. M. Borba, A. M. P. do Santos, and A. C. Colonese. 2021: Fishing intensification as response to Late Holocene socio-ecological instability in southeastern South America. *Scientific Reports* 11:23506.
- Villafaña, J. A., S. Hernandez, A. Alvarado, K. Shimada, C. Pimiento, M. M. Rivadeneira, and J. Kriwet. 2020: First evidence of a palaeo-nursery area of the great white shark. *Scientific Reports* 10:8502.
- Visaggi, C., and S. J. Godfrey. 2010: Variation in composition and abundance of Miocene shark teeth from Calvert Cliffs, Maryland. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 30:26–35.